

TOOLSHED USER GUIDE

SHARING SOLUTIONS Sustainability
Impact Assessment (SIA) Tools

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SHARING SOLUTIONS
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SHARING
SOLUTIONS

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Sustainability Impact Assessment (SIA) tools

Toolshed User Guide

1. Introduction

Welcome to the user guide for the Toolshed section of SHARING SOLUTIONS. This document explains what the Toolshed can be used for and how to use it.

1.1 What's in the Toolshed?

The Toolshed is a flexible reporting resource. It does not prescribe how initiatives should measure their impact. Instead, it provides a framework for initiatives to understand where they are having impact, to support more robust reporting practices and to help communicate impacts. The Toolshed automatically creates a visual summary report of the social, environmental, economic, and governance data entered, connecting that data to the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) so that it can be easily understood by your stakeholders. The Toolshed also provides you with a detailed impact report and an Excel spreadsheet with your sustainability data, to help maximise your impacts.

Once you have registered and logged onto the SHARING SOLUTIONS portal, you will be able to access the Toolshed from the side menu. Here you will find two options for your Sustainability Impact Assessment (SIA) reporting: i) the Starter SIA tool and the ii) Main SIA tool.

The two assessments differ significantly in the level of information required and in their output:

- The Starter SIA is a simple tool to understand your broad impacts on sustainability.
- The Main SIA is more advanced and allows you to do a full sustainability impact assessment of your food sharing initiative.

Starter SIA Tool

Upon clicking on the Starter SIA button, you will be prompted to answer 34 questions. These only require checking either the 'yes' or 'no' boxes provided. You can add further information under 'tell us more'. Once completed, simply click submit and a one-page summary report will be generated detailing which SDGs you are contributing to.

Please refer to [Section 2.2](#) of this User Guide for a step-by-step guide.

Main SIA Tool

Upon clicking on the Main SIA tool button, you click the 'Start' button to commence your full sustainability report. Data entry takes place under the four main pillars: social, environmental, economic and governance. Each pillar has a number of impact areas (see [Table 1](#)) and questions that you can select from to reflect your initiatives focus and the data you have available to you.

Upon completing the Main SIA assessment, you will receive a summary report about the impact your initiative is having in each sustainability pillar with precise graphics to help your organization identify your best performing impact areas.

Please refer to [Section 2.3](#) of this User Guide for a step-by-step guide.

1.2 Why use the Toolshed?

The Toolshed provides a resource to help you understand and communicate your impacts on the sustainability of food systems and provides guidance on how you might improve your impact reporting.

Sustainability reporting can help you:

- Monitor progress towards your goals
- Communicate the impact of what you do
- Demonstrate the impact of your activities to those who regulate or support you
- Showcase your impacts to attract new stakeholders to your activities
- Inspire others to develop similarly impactful activities in other places

1.3 Who is the Toolshed for?

If you are an organisation, network or informal group of people who come together to grow, cook, eat or redistribute food together as part of your activities, then the Toolshed is for you. The Toolshed has been designed for initiatives which may be small-scale or not for profit as these types of initiatives are not well-served by existing reporting frameworks.

1.4 How was the Toolshed designed?

The Toolshed has adapted and extended international frameworks for sustainability impact assessment in the light of research conducted by the SHARCITY project, funded by the European Research Council, which mapped and analysed thousands of food sharing initiatives internationally. More detailed information on the development of the Toolshed can be found in this open access research paper [\[link\]](#). The Toolshed was updated and upgraded in 2023, under an ERC Proof of Concept grant, to form SHARING SOLUTIONS.

2. Creating a sustainability impact assessment

You can create your sustainability impact report using whatever data you have collected to date. There are over 100 impact questions to choose from, but no questions are compulsory. Because the tool is designed to be useful for different kinds of food sharing initiatives not all questions will be relevant to your activities. These questions are placed under four pillars of sustainability – social, environmental, economic and governance. In turn, these pillars are sub-divided into impact areas that are represented in Table 1.

Table 1: The 4 Sustainability Pillars and 13 Impact Areas of the Toolshed

Social	Environmental	Economic	Governance
Community integration increasing community integration through food sharing	Agricultural practices enhancing biodiversity, soil and ecosystem health	Jobs creating decent and accessible jobs	Civic engagement helping to tackle wider societal and policy issues
Access & affordability improving the accessibility of fresh nutritious food for all	Food waste reducing food loss and waste	Local food production utilising land to produce food and food products	Strategic planning engaging with relevant stakeholders and policy making
Health & wellbeing improving health and well-being outcomes	Carbon footprint reducing GHGs from the food system	Affordability improving the affordability of fresh nutritious food	Risk Control managing risks to the continued operations of the initiative

Education

Raising awareness in order to influence behaviour and improve the sustainability of the food system from economic, environmental, governance and social perspectives

Each impact area has a set of questions where data can be entered to record and communicate the impacts of your initiative. Remember, you can answer as few or as many indicators as are relevant to your initiative. This tool is not designed to reward those who report the most impact areas, but rather to help you and others understand the specific impacts of your initiative. In using the Toolshed you may come across indicators or impact areas you have not previously considered or had time to collect the relevant data for. We provide guidance on how you can start to collect relevant data to report on Indicators within the tool.

2.1 Getting started

The first step in using the Toolshed is to create a user profile for the SHARING SOLUTIONS Toolkit. You can register for SHARING SOLUTIONS by answering a few questions about your initiative [here](#). Once your registration has been approved by the SHARING SOLUTIONS team, you can create a profile in the user dashboard and begin creating a SIA report for your initiative.

2.2 Starter SIA Tool Instructions

1. Click on the Starter SIA 'Start' button.
2. Answer the 34 yes or no questions (based off the impact areas in Table 1).
3. You can skip questions if not relevant to your Food Sharing Initiative.
4. You can add more details about how you contribute to this impact area by clicking 'tell us more', as shown in Figure 1.
5. Once you have answered all the questions relative to your initiative, click the 'submit questions' button.
6. You will now be able to download a summary report of your Food Sharing Initiative (item A in Figure 2) or an Excel spreadsheet of your answers (item B in Figure 2) for your perusal.
7. See an example [here](#).

Figure 1: Starter SIA interface, answering questions in a 'yes' or 'no' manner, with the option of adding more details by clicking the 'tell us more' button.

Figure 2: Click on 'Submit answers' to generate reports A and B.

2.3 Main SIA Tool Instructions

1. Click Start
2. Browse questions across impact areas within the four pillars and relative impact areas, as highlighted in Table 1.
3. Each impact area will prompt you to a set of questions relative to the impact area you have chosen, as shown in Figure 3.
4. Please note you do not have to complete your report in one go, you are able to resume your Main SIA assessment as you wish.

Figure 3: Layout of Main SIA tool

5. You only need to answer relevant questions to your Food Sharing Initiative, and are free to skip any questions which do not apply to your initiative.
6. You can provide qualitative and/or quantitative data for most questions.
7. Once you have completed submitting data for your assessment, head to the 'Governance' pillar and click the 'Submit' button at the bottom of the page. (See Figure 4)

Figure 4: Location of submit button

8. The next page will help you choose the top impact areas that you want to highlight in your report. You will be prompt with a list of questions you have filled in, of which you can select up to 3 indicators which represent areas of significant impact for your initiative.
9. You can now select your top three word-based answers (qualitative data) to be included in your summary report and your top tree number-based answers (quantitative data) to be included in your summary report, see Figure 5. These choices will be displayed within your summary report.

The screenshot shows a web interface titled 'Context and emphasis'. It contains two main sections: 'Your impact in words (qualitative questions)' and 'Your impacts in numbers (quantitative questions)'. In the qualitative section, there are four items with expand/collapse icons: 'Diverting organic waste from landfill' (minus), 'Reducing the carbon footprint of the food system' (plus, circled in red), 'Contributing to policy development' (plus), and 'Stakeholder engagement' (plus). The quantitative section has three items: 'Increasing appreciation of different cultures across and within communities' (minus), 'Connecting and creating new support networks within communities' (plus), and 'Reducing the carbon footprint of the food system' (plus). A 'Preview & Confirm' button is circled in red at the bottom right. A 'Back' button is at the bottom left. A progress indicator shows '2 of 2'.

Figure 5: Choosing your top three answers to describe your organisation qualitative and quantitative sustainable impact.

10. Click 'Preview & Confirm' and see what your summary report will look like
11. Click 'Publish' to generate three Main SIA outputs:
 - a. A three-page graphical summary report
 - b. A full SIA report and
 - c. An Excel spreadsheet of your sustainability data.

Your summary report will also include overall graphics showing your impact across the four pillars, including an overview of how much your initiative is contributing to each SDG. This indicates whether you are: (1) Contributing to the general ethos of a goal, (2) Having a direct impact on a goal; and (3) Having a major impact on a goal.

12. See an example report [here](#).
13. You can go back and edit your report by clicking 'Modify' at the bottom of the preview page.
14. If you are happy with the report, then click 'Publish'.
15. Download your Summary Report and / or your Full report. You can also choose to share your summary report with other stakeholders on the Talent Garden by requesting to share your impact report, as shown in Figure 6.

Hi, EN

Impact Assessment Completed

Congratulations on completing your sustainability impact assessment report! You can now download your full impact report and a shorter summary report. If you would like to share your summary report on Facebook or Twitter then please add the relevant information below. You can also choose to share your summary report in our Talent Garden.

[DOWNLOAD SUMMARY REPORT](#) [DOWNLOAD FULL REPORT](#)

SHARE A REPORT

Twitter Handle

Facebook Handle

Would you like to share your impact summary with others in our Talent Garden? Yes No

[Share](#)

Figure 6: Downloading report and choosing whether to showcase your report with SHARING SOLUTIONS Talent Garden.

3. Indicators, data collection and useful resources

This section will help you with data collection and impact reporting both generally and for individual indicators in the Toolshed.

3.1 Creating a sustainability impact assessment report

The Toolshed can create sustainability impact assessment reports from any data added by you. Ideally data inputted to the Toolshed should represent a 12-month period so that can comprise an annual report for your initiative. However, this may not always be possible. Data sets might be incomplete for a 12-month period, your initiative may be less than 12-months old or you might be required to report over different periods for other stakeholders. This does not prohibit you from using the Toolshed and we provide supports to help you build towards annual reporting.

3.2 Choosing sample sizes when creating surveys

To ensure that the results of any participant surveys you conduct reflects the target population as precisely as possible it is useful to determine how many people you need to interview in order to get results that reflect the target population as precisely as needed. You can determine a representative sample by using this [Sample Size Calculator](#).

For example, if 1000 participants attend your cooking classes over a year, you may like to know how many participants have increased confidence in their cooking abilities due to attending your class. Rather than surveying all 1000 participants you can determine a reasonable sample size using this calculator to ensure that your smaller survey is sufficiently representative. In this example if you are happy to have a margin of error of +/-5% in the number of participants that answer yes and be 95% confident in this result then an appropriate sample size is 278. We advise that where possible margins of error of 5% or less are used to determine appropriate sample size for quantitative data.

3.3 Information required for using the Toolshed

This section is designed to help you understand what information you will need to create your report in the Toolshed. Table 2 is designed to help users understand which indicators in the Toolshed are relevant to them, the data they might need to report their impact for this indicator and any external resources that may help them with this.

Table 2 contains:

- The impact areas contained in the Toolshed
- A short explanation of the kinds of activities that might provide data for those impact areas
- A summary of the data collection options to report your impact

In the Toolshed it is always possible to give a qualitative description of relevant activities and impacts of your initiative for each indicator. This might include relevant testimonials from employees, volunteers, participants or users of any services your initiative provides.

For many of the indicators in the Toolshed it is also possible to ask your participants, volunteers or employees specific questions in order to generate useful quantitative data. Should you need help in collecting data, please contact the SHARING SOLUTIONS consultancy team, who will be able to help you generate ad-hoc surveys and data collection strategies to help you and your initiative generate specific qualitative and/or quantitative data.

For some questions several options for data collection may be available, answering any of the options will allow you to report an indicator in the Toolshed. You can answer multiple questions if you have the relevant information. Should you need help in collecting and reporting data for your sustainability impact assessment, please do not hesitate to contact the SHARING SOLUTIONS team for support at info@sharingsolutions.eu.

Table 2. A list of all indicators in the Toolshed along with a summary of the data collection options and links to useful resources for each indicator

Indicator	Relevance	Data collection options
1. Increasing appreciation of different cultures across and within communities	This may include providing a space for, or holding events that encourage, people from different sections of society to come together around food.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keeping a record of people attending events (level 1) • Survey of participants (level 2)
2. Improving communication skills	Providing opportunities for people who find communication challenging, or who are not fluent in the national language, to interact with others in a supportive setting allows them to improve their language and communication skills.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey of participants (level 2)
3. Fostering a wider food and sharing culture	Collaborating and connecting with other food sharing initiatives to learn from and inspire each other.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Record of other initiatives you share knowledge or collaborate with (level 1) • Survey of current and former employees or volunteers (or both)
4. Increased access to and consumption of fruit and vegetables	Examples include distributing fruit and vegetables to low-income communities or creating opportunities for people to taste new varieties of fruit and vegetables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calculation of fruit and vegetable portion sizes (level 1) • Survey of participants (level 2 or 3)

5. Increased access to and consumption of fresh food.	Fresh food is defined as food that is not preserved by processes like canning, dehydration, freezing and smoking. Activities can include supporting people to grow, store, prepare and/or eat fresh food.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of participants using the facilities that are likely to increase access to fresh or freshly prepared food (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2)
6. Connecting and creating new support networks within communities.	Creating opportunities for people to socialise and discuss what is going on in their lives on a regular basis.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey of participants (level 3)
7. Boosting levels of meal sharing	Increasing the number of meals people eat together with others improves well-being.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keeping a record of who is coming to any canteens or other shared eating events (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2)
8. Increasing well-being through volunteering	Volunteering with food sharing initiatives is likely to be having a positive impact on volunteers' lives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey of participants (level 2)
9. Improving self- confidence and resilience	Food sharing activities can improve self-confidence, self-worth and happiness among participants, improving resilience in individuals.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey of participants (level 2 or 3)
10. Increasing movement and exercise	Food sharing activities can contribute to the amount of moderate exercise people are getting, e.g. through helping to harvest crops at a community garden.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keeping a record of people who engaged in exercise (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2)

11. Increasing access to health and well-being services	Food sharing events can provide opportunities to encourage people (particularly vulnerable or marginalised groups) to access important services for health and well-being.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of participants who gained greater access to health services (level 1 or 2)
12. Thinking about issues beyond price when buying food	Choosing to buy locally-sourced products or organic products are just some of the additional considerations which participants may be thinking about more following engagement with food sharing initiatives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey of participants (level 2)
13. Increasing engagement in growing food	Food sharing initiatives can inspire people to grow more of their own food, engaging them more directly in how food is produced.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of participants who grew their own food (level 1 or 2)
14. Increased confidence and participation in cooking	Learning to cook alongside others can improve diets and wellbeing, as well as reduce loneliness and increase social capital.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of people to come to your cooking events (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2)
15. Discovery of new fresh foods	The discovery and enjoyment of new fresh foods can enrich peoples' lives. This can be particularly important for young people who are still forming their relationship with food.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of people to come to your food tasting events (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2)
16. Diverting organic waste from landfill	Composting material and/or accepting organic material from others in the food system, as well as sending organic material generated from food sharing activities for composting off-site, all count towards this indicator.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Estimate of how many tonnes of organic waste your initiative diverted from landfill (level 1) Track the number of people to come to your composting events (level 1)

17. Water recovery	Impacts can come from both implementing techniques to reduce water use and by demonstrating these techniques to others.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of people to come to your water recovery events (level 1) Estimate the annual recovery of water (level 2)
18. Maintaining and improving soil quality	Initiatives which manage urban green spaces can play a vital role in maintaining and improving urban soil quality on their land to preserve its potential for producing food and providing other vital ecosystem services in the future.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tests of soil quality conducted on growing sites Describe any techniques you use to improve soil quality on land
19. Maintaining and improving biodiversity	Any initiative which owns or manages green spaces in their community can make a positive contribution to biodiversity in the surrounding area.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct biodiversity monitoring study
20. Food waste reduction	Diverting edible surplus food away from landfill to be consumed by people could include collaborating with food businesses or charities, using donations of surplus food, or supporting people to consciously change their food practices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Count the number of people to come to your food waste reduction events (level 1) Track the amount of food wasted by your initiative (level 2) Survey of participants (level 2)
21. Reducing the carbon footprint of the food system	Over a third of global greenhouse gas emissions caused by humans come from our food system. Food sharing initiatives can influence people and businesses to reduce the carbon footprint embodied in their food choices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of people to come to your carbon footprint events (level 1) Calculate the figure for carbon emissions avoided through your initiative's activities (level 3)
22. Increasing preference for vegetarian meals	Food sharing initiatives which are encouraging people to eat more fresh fruit and vegetables and less meat are having a positive effect on the environmental sustainability of food systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Count the number of people to come to your food choice events (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2 or 3)

23. Reducing food packaging	Many initiatives play an important role by changing people's attitude to issues of packaging and the waste they generate through their food choices.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of people to come to your food packaging and/or reduce waste events (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2 or 3)
24. Training and jobs	Initiatives which run formal training or employment schemes can help people find routes to formal qualifications and ultimately secure jobs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track number of participants who have come through formal training schemes run by your initiative and have found work afterwards (level 1) Survey of current and former employees/volunteers (level 2 or 3)
25. Fairly paid work	In many cases food initiatives can have an important economic and cultural impact through providing stable and fairly paid employment in the food sector. This indicator is only relevant for initiatives that have paid staff.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Count number of your employees paid at a rate of 10% or more or equal to the hourly legal minimum wage in your country (level 1) Count number of your employees paid at full time living wage in your country (level 2)
26. Contribution to food production	Increasing food production, through food sharing, can provide greater access to fresh food, provide people with a greater sense of connection to how food is produced and increase pride in local food cultures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the food produced by your initiative (level 1) Track the amount of newly secured land (level 1) Calculate the amount of food produced per m² (level 2)
27. Reducing pressure on food budgets	Providing low-cost or free food to people who need it or providing knowledge about food budgeting practices can have a direct financial benefit (quantifiable) and can also help relieve anxiety and stress (qualitative benefit).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey of participants (level 2 or 3)

28. Sharing specific skills and knowledge about the food system	Increasing general knowledge about the food system is important for sustainability as it helps people reconnect with the food they eat.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Track the number of people to come to your food system events (level 1) Survey of participants (level 2)
29. Formal qualifications	Food sharing initiatives sometimes run, or contribute to, training and educational programmes which lead to formal qualifications such as diplomas or industry recognised certificates for the participants.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Count the number of people who gained formal qualifications (level 1) Survey of current and former employees/volunteers (level 2)
30. Contributing to policy development	Food sharing initiatives sometimes contribute to, or encourage their participants to engage with, policy issues such as urban food strategy development and community consultations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survey of participants (level 2)
31. Sharing knowledge and good practice	Initiatives can play a vital role in actively promoting the practices and techniques they are using to tackle important issues in the food system and influencing others to adopt them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Solely qualitative data collection</i>
32. Strategic planning and sustainability	Having a strategic plan which formally states the goals of an initiative can help to focus attention on the most important outputs and where to focus energy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Solely qualitative data collection</i>
33. Stakeholder engagement	Successful food sharing initiatives often have strategies that identify, engage with and manage ongoing relationships with other stakeholders.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Solely qualitative data collection</i>
34. Risk control	The long-term viability of food sharing initiatives depends upon identifying risks and controlling for them. This could include the diversity and security of funding sources or the type of access you have to the land or spaces that you use.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Solely qualitative data collection</i>

4. Glossary

Some of the phrases used in the Toolshed may not be familiar to everyone or may be used differently in other documents on sustainability impact assessment. Below is a short glossary of important terms we use in the Toolshed and this user guide.

Food sharing – Food sharing involves collective actions around food and food related items, spaces, skills and knowledge. It can take place between friends, families, neighbours, communities and strangers across the food system from growing, cooking, and eating to surplus food redistribution.

Food Sharing Initiative (FSI) – A Food Sharing Initiative (FSI) is a group, network or organization which includes specific food-sharing activities for people to come together to reduce food waste by redistributing surplus harvests and food products. Initiatives may be not-for-profit or for-profit and adopt a range of institutional structures from co-operatives to social enterprise. FSIs adopt different organisational forms, including co-operatives and social enterprises, charities and for-profits and can be community, private sector or state-led. Examples include, seed libraries, community gardens, food related co-operatives, community kitchens, and surplus food redistribution organisations.

Impact area – clusters similar indicator questions within sustainability pillars (Table 1).

Indicator – An indicator provides a simple and reliable means to capture information at a particular point and which can be used over time to identify changes. The Toolshed offers over 100 indicator questions to choose from, the user need only answer the questions relevant to their work.

Quantitative indicator – a pure number, an index, ratio or percentage. Quantitative indicators allow easy comparison of the status of the same indicator at different times and can enable simple comparisons between the performances or achievements of two or more organizations.

Qualitative indicator – depict the status of something in qualitative terms (words) which involves judgement and or grading. For example, the extent to which participants in food sharing initiatives feel that community cohesion is enhanced by food sharing.

Stakeholders – A stakeholder for food sharing initiatives is a person, group or organization that has interest in or influence over their activities, such as volunteers and employees, food retailers, the government (and its agencies), and the community.

Sustainability – In the Toolshed sustainability is used to refer to the capacity of a system to survive and persist over time in a place. It draws on the concept of sustainable development, which was defined by the Brundtland Commission as: "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs".

Sustainability Impact Assessment (SIA) – SIA is an approach for exploring the combined economic, environmental and social impacts of policies, programmes, strategies, plans and activities. Such assessments can also assist decision making and strategic planning throughout the entire policy cycle.

Sustainability pillar – Describes the four main elements of sustainability- social, environment, economy, and governance.

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